

MODELING LARYNGEAL MOTOR CONTROL WITH SOMATOSENSORY FEEDBACK FOR PREPHONATORY VOCAL POSTURE

Nicolás F. Quinteros^{1,2}, Jesús A. Parra², Gabriel A. Alzamendi^{3,4}, Matías Zañartu^{1,2}

¹ Department of Electronic Engineering, Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María, Valparaíso, Chile

² Advanced Center for Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María, Valparaíso, Chile

³ Institute for Research and Development on Bioengineering and Bioinformatics (IBB), CONICET-UNER, Oro Verde, Entre Ríos 3100, Argentina

⁴ Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Nacional de Entre Ríos, Entre Ríos, Argentina

Keywords: Somatosensory Feedback, Prephonatory Vocal Posture, Laryngeal Motor Control

Introduction & rationale: The adjustment of vocal fold posture from a resting respiratory state to a proper prephonatory posture is a critical aspect of laryngeal motor control, involving the rapid and synergistic coordination of the intrinsic laryngeal muscles (ILM). This transition, occurring before any sound is produced, creates a unique environment in which the somatosensory mechanisms responsible for vocal control can be isolated and examined. Despite its importance, the role of somatosensory feedback in prephonatory posturing remains poorly understood. Recent reviews by Hernández-Morato et al. (2023) and Kent (2024) suggest that somatosensory feedback plays a pivotal role in fine-tuning laryngeal motor control, especially during rapid transitions. Existing neurocomputational models of laryngeal motor control (Weerathunge et al., 2022, Palaparthi et al, 2024) have limited representations of laryngeal somatosensory feedback at the prephonatory stage, which in turn limits their ability to accurately simulate the role of laryngeal proprioceptive and tactile feedback in motor adaptation tasks in this transient phase. By developing a model of laryngeal motor control that integrates somatosensory feedback during the prephonatory phase, insights can be gained into the feedback mechanisms for reaching a phonatory steady state of vocal posture. Our hypothesis posits that a selective set of somatosensory features is essential for achieving and maintaining accurate laryngeal posture prior to phonation, offering potential insights and advances in understanding vocal pathologies.

Objective: To develop a physiologically relevant somatosensory feedback scheme that incorporates prephonatory gestures for a neurocomputational model of laryngeal motor control.

Methods: The triangular body-cover model (TBCM) (Alzamendi et al., 2022), based on the work of Titze and Hunter (2007), was used to represent vocal posture dynamics during the prephonatory phase, simulating the relationship between ILM activations and the resulting glottal configuration. The model inputs consisted of the normalized activations between 0 (no activation) and 1 (full activation) for the five ILM: cricothyroid (CT), thyroarytenoid (TA), lateral cricoarytenoid (LCA), interarytenoid (IA), and posterior cricoarytenoid (PCA). Prephonatory posture is described by four biomechanical features: vocal process coordinates (ξ, ψ), arytenoid rotation angle (θa), and vocal fold length (Lg).

Iteratively solving the complete set of differential equations in the TBCM (plant model) for each configuration within a motor control framework is computationally expensive. Here, a deep neural network regressor was employed to approximate the nonlinear relationships between ILM activations and biomechanical outcomes, significantly reducing computational costs while preserving predictive accuracy. Training data were drawn from a total of 161,051 simulations performed that comprehensively map the steady-state laryngeal configurations, corresponding to 0.1 increments for each of the normalized ILM activations, as shown in Figure 1. Feature importance analysis revealed that PCA was crucial for predicting ξ and θa , CT strongly influenced ψ and Lg , TA was significant for ψ and Lg , while LCA and IA explained poorly the features.

Somatosensory-feedback control of vocal posture was implemented using an inverse Jacobian method, iteratively adjusting motor commands based on somatosensory errors to refine muscle activations and achieve the target vocal configurations. Given the sensitivity of the control model to initial muscle activations, ILM were initialized at an activation level of 0.1, with a standard deviation of 0.001 across 100 Monte Carlo simulations to assess control consistency. The simulations of the prephonatory vocal posture control

Figure 1: Vocal posture simulations obtained from the TBCM.

model were conducted using ILM activations as inputs and two different sets of proprioceptive somatosensory outputs: one with four features and another with three features, excluding Lg . The rationale behind simulating both conditions was to evaluate whether vocal posture can be effectively defined using only purely proprioceptive features (ξ, ψ , and θa) without relying on Lg , which also involves mechanoreceptive feedback. While Lg integrates the influence of all

muscles, it was excluded to prioritize direct proprioceptive control strategies and assess how the remaining outputs alone could drive stable phonatory postures.

Results: In Figure 2, the left column shows the muscle activation trajectories over time, while the right column presents the evolution of four proprioceptive outputs: (ξ, ψ) , θ_a , and Lg . The system effectively stabilizes these outputs, reaching the target vocal posture with ILM activations converging close to their expected values (0% PCA, 50% LCA, 90% IA, 20% TA, 20% CT). On the other hand, Figure 3 removes Lg as somatosensory information to be controlled, slightly reducing the accuracy of ILM activation estimation and motor control compared to the case with four variables. Although Lg is not used as a control variable but only as a hidden state, the intended vocal process remains well-defined. This highlights that while the inclusion of Lg enhances the precision of achieving target activations, its absence provides a clearer evaluation of the role of purely proprioceptive features in vocal motor control.

Figure 2: Trajectories of ILM activations to reach a target vocal posture described by four somatosensory features. Figure 3: Trajectories of ILM activations to reach a target vocal posture described by three somatosensory features.

Conclusions: This study developed a somatosensory feedback-based model of vocal posture motor control, which provides a novel approach to studying how prephonatory motor control is regulated. Results show that three key proprioceptive biomechanical features are sufficient to achieve and maintain a stable vocal posture, even without explicitly controlling vocal fold elongation. While including one contributes to improved accuracy in targeting muscle activations, excluding one demonstrated that proprioceptive signals alone can also effectively drive prephonatory control. These findings reinforce the idea that proprioceptive feedback plays a critical role in vocal motor control, shaping how the larynx is stabilized prior to phonation.

Future work will focus on refining the model with adaptive learning strategies, similar to the DIVA (Tourville et al., 2011) and LaDIVA (Weerathunge et al, 2022) models, and assessing how these control mechanisms can differ in typical and hyperfunctional voices.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) National Institute on Deafness and Other Communication Disorders grant P50 DC015446, ANID grants FONDECYT 1230828, BASAL AFB240002, and National PhD Scholarship 21240471.

References:

Alzamendi, G. A., Peterson, S. D., Erath, B. D., Hillman, R. E., & Zañartu, M. (2022). Triangular body-cover model of the vocal folds with coordinated activation of the five intrinsic laryngeal muscles. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 151(1), 17-30.

Hernández-Morato, I., Yu, V. X., & Pitman, M. J. (2023). A review of the peripheral proprioceptive apparatus in the larynx. *Frontiers in Neuroanatomy*, 17, 1114817.

Kent, R. D. (2024). The Feel of Speech: Multisystem and Polymodal Somatosensation in Speech Production. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 67(5), 1424-1460.

Palaparathi, A., Alluri, R. K., & Titze, I. R. (2024). Deep Learning for Neuromuscular Control of Vocal Source for Voice Production. *Applied Sciences*, 14(2), 769.

Titze, I. R., & Hunter, E. J. (2007). A two-dimensional biomechanical model of vocal fold posturing. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 121(4), 2254-2260.

Tourville, J. A., & Guenther, F. H. (2011). The DIVA model: A neural theory of speech acquisition and production. *Language and cognitive processes*, 26(7), 952-981.

Weerathunge, H. R., Alzamendi, G. A., Cler, G. J., Guenther, F. H., Stepp, C. E., & Zañartu, M. (2022). LaDIVA: A neurocomputational model providing laryngeal motor control for speech acquisition and production. *PLoS computational biology*, 18(6), e1010159.